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Research Article

CERVICAL CANCER-A REVIEW ARTICLE AND REPORTFateme Parooei ¹, Mahmood Anbari ², Morteza Salarzaei ^{1*}¹ Medical student, Student Research Committee, Zabol University of Medical Sciences,
Zabol, Iran² Zabol University of Medical Sciences, Zabol, Iran.**Abstract:**

Introduction: Cervical cancer is the third most common cancer in women in the world. Unlike industrialized countries, poor countries struggle with cervical cancer as one of the most important causes of death. It is quite difficult, and required precise examination and logical suspicion, to diagnose this disease before it kills the patient.

Methods: In this review article, the databases Medline, Cochrane, Science Direct, and Google Scholar were thoroughly searched to identify the Cervical cancer. In this review, the papers published until early January 2017 that were conducted to study Cervical cancer were selected.

About the patient: The patient was a 51-year-old lady who had visited Amiralmounin Hospital in Zabol and had complained of having an irregular bleeding disorder for 2 months. She was examined due the possibility of lesion in the cervix and pathological report confirmed the cervical stone cell carcinoma. Pre-operation ultrasound confirmed the presence of an 8 * 9 cm mass with a specific limit on the left side of the pelvic cavity.

Discussion and conclusion: Only third to breast and endometrial cancers, cervical cancer is one of the most common cancers specific to women; although early diagnosis of this disease makes treatment possible in 95% of cases, the absence of treatment or lack of response to treatment often results in the death of the patient in 95% of cases in only 2 years after diagnosis.

Key words: Cervical, cancer

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INTRODUCTION:

Cervical cancer is the third most common cancer in women in the world. Unlike industrialized countries, poor countries struggle with cervical cancer as one of the most important causes of death (1). It is quite difficult, and required precise examination and logical suspicion, to diagnose this disease before it kills the patient. Although a general decline has been reported in the incidence of cervical invasive cancer in women, recent studies have shown increase in total incidence of this disease (2). The average age of the incidence of cervical cancer is 52.2 years, and the risk factors include sexual activity, especially the onset of sexual contact from an early age, early childbirth, having multiple sex partners, herpes simplex virus, human papillomavirus (HPV) virus, low economic and social status, smoking, history of cervical cancer, and diet (3). Cellular carcinoma is the most common type of invasive cervical cancer; however, the incidence of aggressive and anaplastic tumors has, also, been reported at lower ages. Since there are still numerous unknown factors which affect the incidence of cervical cancer, this disease is, also, possible to emerge in young girls (4). Thus, it is necessary to consider the risk of the incidence of this disease in this group of seemingly safe women.

ABOUT THE PATIENT:

The patient was a 51-year-old lady who had visited Amirmounin Hospital in Zabol and had complained of having an irregular bleeding disorder for 2 months. She was examined due to the possibility of lesion in the cervix and pathological report confirmed the cervical stone cell carcinoma. Pre-operation ultrasound confirmed the presence of an 8 * 9 cm mass with a specific limit on the left side of the pelvic cavity. CT scan was requested to reject possible metastatic, the result of which turned out to be normal. Based on the report of surgery pathology, cervical stem cell carcinoma was a large cell necrosis, with invasion depth of more than 60% of cervical thickness. The patient underwent radiotherapy and chemotherapy followed by 6 sessions of brachytherapy for her cervical cancer. The patient was stable and had no complain in 6-month follow up medical examination.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION:

Only third to breast and endometrial cancers, cervical cancer is one of the most common cancers specific to women; although early diagnosis of this disease makes treatment possible in 95% of cases, the absence of treatment or lack of response to treatment often results in the death of the patient in 95% of cases in only 2 years after diagnosis (5). The average age for the incidence of cervix is 52.2 years, and the age distribution pattern has two

maxima in the age group of 35-39 and 60-64 (6). In addition to the identified risk factors, marrying too young, repeated marriage, history of smoking, birth control pills, diabetes and history of recurrent genital infections are among the most prominent risk factors; there has been no report of cervical cancer in single individuals (7). The importance of low age during the first sexual intercourse seems to be due to the biological changes that occur in the cervix during puberty (8). Sexual activity is a series of events that seem to change the health of the cervix and make it susceptible to cancer. According to a 9-year survey, women under the age of 35 years accounted for only 3.9% of patients with cervical cancer; 50 patients were at Stage Ib, and there was only one single case of anaplastic disorder (9). The 5-year survival rate of Ib patients turned out to be 81.6%, and there was no relationship between the patient's age and survival at this stage. Some studies on cervical cancer have shown that young women with a history have a worse prognosis than older patients (10). While others reported that age has little effect on the prognosis of cervical cancer, a 24-year study that examined screening as a prognostic factor for cervical cancer showed the overall 5-year-survival rate to be 63%; based on this reports, and the most powerful parameters turned out to be disease stage, histological diagnosis, the patient's age at the time of diagnosis, and screening participation, in order (11).

REFERENCES:

1. Smith JS, Lindsay L, Hoots B, Keys J, Franceschi S, Winer R, Clifford GM. Human papillomavirus type distribution in invasive cervical cancer and high-grade cervical lesions: a meta-analysis update. *International journal of cancer*. 2007 Aug 1;121(3):621-32.
2. Schiffman M, Castle PE, Jeronimo J, Rodriguez AC, Wacholder S. Human papillomavirus and cervical cancer. *The Lancet*. 2007 Sep 14;370(9590):890-907.
3. de Sanjose S, Quint WG, Alemany L, Geraets DT, Klaustermeier JE, Lloveras B, Tous S, Felix A, Bravo LE, Shin HR, Vallejos CS. Human papillomavirus genotype attribution in invasive cervical cancer: a retrospective cross-sectional worldwide study. *The lancet oncology*. 2010 Nov 30;11(11):1048-56.
4. Cuzick J, Clavel C, Petry KU, Meijer CJ, Hoyer H, Ratnam S, Szarewski A, Birembaut P, Kulasingam S, Sasieni P, Iftner T. Overview of the European and North American studies on HPV testing in primary cervical cancer screening. *International Journal of Cancer*. 2006 Sep 1;119(5):1095-101.
5. Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC). Cervical cancer screening among women

aged 18-30 years-United States, 2000-2010. MMWR. Morbidity and mortality weekly report. 2013 Jan 4;61(51-52):1038.

6.Khan MJ, Castle PE, Lorincz AT, Wacholder S, Sherman M, Scott DR, Rush BB, Glass AG, Schiffman M. The elevated 10-year risk of cervical precancer and cancer in women with human papillomavirus (HPV) type 16 or 18 and the possible utility of type-specific HPV testing in clinical practice. *Journal of the National Cancer Institute*. 2005 Jul 20;97(14):1072-9.

7.Behzadmehr R, Keikhaie KR, Pour NS. The Study of Pregnant Women's Attitude toward Using Ultrasound in Pregnancy and its Diagnostic Value based on the Demographic Features in Amir-al-Momenin Hospital of Zabol. *Int J Adv Res Biol Sci*. 2017;4(6):58-63.

8.Behzadmehr R, Keikhaie KR, Pour NS. The Study of Pregnant Women's Attitude toward Using Ultrasound in Pregnancy and its Diagnostic Value based on the Demographic Features in Amir-al-

Momenin Hospital of Zabol. *Int J Adv Res Biol Sci*. 2017;4(6):58-63.

9.Kahkhaie KR, Keikha F, Keikhaie KR, Abdollahimohammad A, Salehin S. Perinatal Outcome After Diagnosis of Oligohydramnios at Term. *Iranian Red Crescent Medical Journal*. 2014 May;16(5).

10.Shahraki Z, Keikhaie KR, Amjadi N, Bonjar ZH, Jahantigh H, Doosti F, Shirazi M. Correlation of 4 Hour Urine Samples with 24-Hour Urine Samples for the Diagnosis of Preeclampsia. *Journal of Obstetrics, Gynecology and Cancer Research*. 2017(In Press).

11.Shirazi M, Hantoush-Zadeh S, Rezaie-Keikhaie K, Pirjani R. Spontaneous Uterine Rupture and Live Fetus in 21th Week of Pregnancy with Hemorrhagic Shock Due to Placenta Percreta: A Case Report. *Case Reports in Clinical Practice*. 2016 Jan 20;1(1):19-21.